

INVESTIGATION OF A NEW DESIGN: TRASH COMPRESSOR BIN (TCB)

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, the trash has become more visible and observed around public places where the Municipal cleaners are not available everyday such as football pitches, public parking, and parks which causes environmental pollution and leaves negative impacts on tourism. As an article in *United Arab Emirates Ministry of climate change & environment* reports that 2.1kg of trash is produced in daily basis due to high population growth and economic development. In other words, this environmental issue is mainly caused by population growth. By using innovated ideas and technologies, the consequences of this problem can be minimized. There are major projects can reduce the waste and there are minor ones. The concentration will be on compressing the trash. The concept of this idea is to use compressing methods to save time and effort of people which are three in the market, manual, hydraulic and automatic. Manual and hydraulic requires people's effort to do the action, however the automatic one works by electricity and more suitable in places where the cleaners are low and doesn't require effort to use. In addition, there are limitations of features on some of the products. For example, some of products work by solar energy, but can't work indoors using electricity. Some of them have both but doesn't have safety system. Our proposed idea will have extra features that will make the automatic bin more efficient and useful for the society.

INTRODUCTION

There are many different types of approaches to follow that will guide people to think of an innovated idea that will have a big impact in solving an issue in a certain aspect. The approach that helped the team to come up with the trash compressor bin idea was something called first-hand experience. As an article in *Humanitarian innovation fund* reports that put yourself in the place of problem holder and perform what they do ("Observe The Problem," n.d.). This means that be in a position where you face the problem and think of an idea to solve it. The situation that the idea was generated from was when one of the team members saw stack of empty bottles thrown near the trash bin in a football pitch due the bin being full. Then he used his hands to pressure down the empty bottles to make more space for the bottles out the bin. This observation led to many questions in his mind, one of the was "Why can't we have an automatic system to compress the trash?". Moreover, this led us to make a survey on SurveyMonkey website to gain more information about

the incident. As seen in figure (8) in appendix, most of responses came from employees in Q1 and the gender or age doesn't matter in this survey. In Q2 figure (9), most of responders have been in a situation where the trash bin was full. In Q3 figure (10), answers were between public places and playing grounds, so our focus will be on these two categories, however, we will add features that make our product be used indoors to increase appealing of the product in the market. In Q4 we asked people what their feelings were in that situation and the responses can be seen in figure (11). In Q5 figure (12), people's reaction was between option A & B when they see a trash bin full of garbage, putting trash near the bin will cause in gather of insects and animals in the area and looking for empty bin will result in wasting their time and effort. In Q6 figure (13), people were asked about the most type of garbage that will make the trash bin full, the responses were close, and we will consider all options as a problem of the project. In Q7 figure (14), people agreed on compressing the garbage will create more space in the bin. In Q8 figure (15), the team proposed three different types of compressing method and they preferred to the automatic method. In Q9 figure (16), people think the automatic compressor will solve bins being full of trash problem. Final question's responses indicate that people would like to buy this product or use it in public if the price was reasonable which can be seen in figure (17). This survey showed that people have faced this problem and think compressing method will solve this matter which led the team to advance in their process to designing stages.

GENERATING IDEAS

There are several techniques that can be used to generate ideas that will lead to successful thinking in creating an innovated project. First one is the most used technique which is brainstorming as seen in figure (1). This method made it possible to reach to the desired outcome and presented the combination of the team ideas in one picture. It starts with general idea which was waste management. Then, it started narrowing down till the desired solution reached which was the automatic trash compressor bin and the possible features that can be added to it to make it more appealing in the market.

Figure 1 Brainstorming

Second technique that was useful in generating ideas was why-why-why analysis. This approach made it easier to imagine the problem and it by asking why 5 times as seen in figure (2). As an article in *Kanbanize* states that Sakichi Toyoda, a Japanese inventor and

Figure 2 Why-Why-why analysis

APPROACH TO INNOVATION

According to generating knowledge tools that were used in this report that made the approach to innovation fast and clear by putting the ideas in one picture that will solve an environmental issue which is trash bins being full. In addition, seeking help and guidance from experts and engineers will make the cloud of ideas to a realistic form. From the knowledge that was received from the survey to searches that were done on the internet. It can be said that most products in the market use compressing bins for kitchen and indoor places. Also, it takes big sacrifice of space to fit it in the desired place. As Carte reports as of most models are built-in, under-the-counter units, perhaps you need to adjust your kitchen cabinets to fit one in. Moreover, the proposed idea will modify the quality of the product by adding features on the trash bin that makes it flexible and be used indoor and outdoor places. First one is the primary skitch of the product as shown in figure (3) where the dimensions of the prototype are identified

Second one is the electric *Figure 3 Primary sketch of the product* is needed to make the system work as shown in figure (4). The system needs four solar panels to give the compressor required power to work in the morning and the excess power will charge the battery, so the system works by battery at night. Arduino is used to control the whole process as desired by programming it. Sensors to indicate trash level. Two LED lights are used, green light indicates that it is safe to throw trash in the bin and the red light is the opposite. SIM 900 is used to send message to the owner that the trash is full. Finally, DC charger is used for indoor usage.

Figure 4 Block diagram

Third one is the 3D module design of the product as figure (5) shows. As seen, there are two shelves, the upper one is where the electric components will be placed and the other one is where the trash container is. The window is where the trash can be thrown in the container.

Figure 5 3D module

Fourth one is the components needed for the project and their budget as table (1) shows.

Table 1 Budget & Parts

Item name	Item image	Item price
Arduino UNO		40 AED
Sensor shield		25 AED
2*Ultrasonic sensor		2*15 =30 AED
SIM900 GSM Module		111.95 AED
4 Channel Relay		30 AED
12V linear actuator		300 AED
Wires		60 AED
12V battery		50 AED
Step down converter		15 AED
Switch		2 AED
12V battery charger		70 AED
Customised Alumunium trash body		350 AED
4 Solar Panels		4*29.27 = 117.08 AED
LED Lights		6.39 AED
Total Amount		1207.39 AED

last one is the final stage of the prototype that was made after many attempts of error as seen in figure (6). Extra figures of the project can be seen in appendices.

In Joseph Schumpeter's theory, this project will be under improved production which will present a better quality of existed ones. The function of the project is that it has a compressor that will condense the garbage such as crate, boxes, and empty bottles when the sensors detect that the bin is full. Then repeat the process till it can't compress anymore. After that, it will send message to the owner that the bin is full. Solar panels that make it useable outdoors and battery charger for indoors. Benefit of the project is that it will increase the efficiency of the bin by making it more usable, it uses clean solar energy to supply the system with power, it has wheels for easy movement and handles for better control. Also, it will eliminate trash bin being full concept as a result it will save customers time and effort for not looking for another empty bin and there will less trash in the place where it is used. This product is made for people who suffered seeing the bin is full in public places and playing grounds, so this product will prevent that.

LIMITATIONS

The project aims to be funded by Dubai SME program that supports small businesses that have potential of success in the market. However, there is a risk that the project gets rejected and it will be difficult to start the business as students who have no incomes. The solution of this risk is that to look for investors like angles or get a bank loan to start the business. The second potential risk is that the demand of the product is low. Promote the product in social media applications and make deals and discounts to get more customers. Last possible risk is that supply parts get damaged and delivered late. Look for better and trustworthy suppliers that offer deals and discounts on parts.

MARKET ANALYSIS

The project is under the environmental problems, waste management and trash collecting sector. Also, it can be considered as renewable energy product since it works by solar. This a huge and big opportunity for this project to be successful in the industry. As an article in *Grand View Research* states that the market size of the smart trash bin in North America in 2017 was 7.4 million USD and predicted to get higher at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.9% till the year 2025 (“North America Smart Trash Bin,” n.d.). This means that smart trash bin market is valuable, and it will be bigger in the upcoming years as the figure (7) states.

Figure 7 Statistics about smart bins

CUSTOMERS & CUSTOMER DEVELOPMENT

Smart trash cans are highly demanded in commercial sector, where the trash waste is generated in huge volume. As an article in *Grand View Research* reports that the commercial sector is particularly in need of automatic garbage bins, since it generates large volumes of waste at hotels, public restrooms, hospitals, and other locations (“North America Smart Trash Bin,” n.d.). This shows that customers could be in commercial sectors or residential one. However, the interviews that were done to 16 random people showed that trash cans problems were in public places and playgrounds. And they are willing to see or pay for a smart trash bin compactor to reduce the volume of trash in those places. The TCB product is fixable which is highly focused to be sold to Municipals that manage wastes in public sector. Then medium focus on commercial sector. Finally, least focus will be in houses.

COMPETITION & POSITIONING

From a realistic point of view, the competition in the success of this product lies in making garbage capable of accommodating more space for garbage and able, for example, to work with clean energy. There are many wastebaskets, but are all of them fulfilling its purpose? When entering the core of competition in this field, we must move forward by thinking about doing something new and capable of making a change from other competing products. In the present time, there are several trash cans that work to recycle trash and benefit from it such as recycling basics from the United States Environmental Protection Agency, and it is expected that soon there will be trash cans

that work with modern technology which is expected to be from companies like Beea'h. It may talk to one who throw the trash, telling him that it is full or not. Also, that it can make it move by saying move around. One of the possible obstacles in the race to enter this competition is that you are new to work in this field, and there are those who preceded you with huge companies and a large budget, which makes it easier for them to manage failure if something happens that you will not be able to deal with.

BUSINESS MODEL AND LEAN STARTUP PHILOSOPHY

After we became clear about the opinions of customers regarding the problem and the most appropriate solution to it, it became clear to us that the product would be of great benefit to them. We decided to join the Amazon platform on the Internet because it is the best solution to translate the idea and turn it into a trade that will benefit us without being obligated to create a special store for us to display the product in, and because e-commerce has become in our time more widespread and desirable for the customer. It is easier to browse and buy products using mobile phones or personal computers. As for the financial plan that that is shown in figure (8), we will receive the initial support from Dubai SME, which will facilitate the startup capital of the project and we expect a loss in the first quarter of the year as shown in the picture below due to the high price of the expenses paid for the acquired expenses, and then there will be a profit in the second quarter And the third and fourth of the year. Financial risks: Low budget or fund/ rejection of the fund is one of the major risks we will face it. Also, low demand of deal It is true that we conducted a survey and took the opinions of customers regarding whether there is rubbish that compresses garbage and how it is useful, but the price may not suit them and there are not many or satisfactory requests for the product.

		First day		Quarter1		Quarter2		Quarter3		Quarter4		
Cashflows out												
	5 Laptops	12,500 AED	Parts	144890.4 AED	Parts	193187.2 AED	Parts	241,484 AED	Parts 1,151*60	289780.8 AED		
			Salary	52,000 AED	Salary	52,000 AED	Salary	52,000 AED	Salary	70,000 AED		
			Packaging delivery	1000 AED	Packaging delivery	1,500 AED	Packaging delivery	2,000 AED	Packaging delivery	2,500 AED		
			Sales promotion & ads	32,000 AED	Sales promotion & ads	7,000 AED	Sales promotion & ads	7,000 AED	Sales promotion & ads	7,000 AED		
			Fulfillment By Amazon (FBA) 3,658.34*3	10,975.02 AED	Fulfillment By Amazon (FBA) 4,717.11*3	14,151.33 AED	Fulfillment By Amazon (FBA) 6280.99*3	18,842.97 AED	Fulfillment By Amazon (FBA) 7851.23*3	23,553.69 AED		
			Referral Fee 216*150	32,400 AED	Referral Fee 216*200	43,000 AED	Referral Fee 216*250	54,000 AED	Referral Fee 216*300	64,800 AED		
	Total Expenses	12,500 AED	Total Expenses	273,265.42 AED	Total Expenses	310,838.53 AED	Total Expenses	375,326.97 AED	Total Expenses	457,634.49 AED	TC	1,429,565.41 AED
Cash flows in	Fund from Dubai SME	286,000 AED	150*1,800 + 10*150 AED delivery	271,500 AED	200*1,800 + 10*200 AED delivery	362,000 AED	250*1,800 + 10*250 AED delivery	452,500 AED	300*1,800 + 10*300 AED delivery	543,000 AED	TR	1,629,000 AED
Balance		273,500	Loss	1,765.42 AED	Profit	51,161.47 AED	Profit	77,173.03 AED	Profit	85,365.51 AED	TN Profit	196,034.59 AED

CONCLUSION

Many people have great innovative ideas and made these thoughts to a real useful product; however, they weren't successful in marketing and business wise and that is because they didn't have guides from expertise about business. The most important lesson that was gained from the experience of researching of primary and secondary information about the problem, to analyzing data, to designing and finalizing the prototype, to knowing customers and competitors, to creating financial plans is that predicting the success of the product or the failure. It can be said that the idea is a true opportunity if some small modifications are done to the design of the project to make it more appealing in the public.

APPENDIX – SURVEY RESULTS

Figure 9 Q1 Responses

Figure 10 Q2 Responses

Where did you face this problem ?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Public places (parking, parks, beaches....etc.)	37.50%	6
Playing grounds (football pitches, tennis, basketball....etc.)	43.75%	7
Indoor places (Malls, house, apartments)	18.75%	3
Other (please specify)	Responses	0
TOTAL		16

Figure 11 Q3 Responses

Trash management issues		SurveyMonkey
Q4 what was your feeling in that situation ?		
Answered: 15 Skipped: 1		
#	RESPONSES	DATE
1	Goof	11/8/2021 6:59 PM
2	Disgusted. Unclean places are not pleasant	11/8/2021 1:54 PM
3	Normal	11/8/2021 11:49 AM
4	It was bad	11/8/2021 11:46 AM
5	Upset	11/8/2021 10:12 AM
6	Bad feeling	11/8/2021 9:16 AM
7	Not feeling comfortable with it Having a bad idea of the cleanliness of the place	11/8/2021 9:13 AM
8	Sad and need a bigger trash can	11/8/2021 8:54 AM
9	Very bad	11/8/2021 8:36 AM
10	bad	11/8/2021 8:25 AM
11	Sad and confused	11/8/2021 8:15 AM
12	Bad	11/8/2021 8:12 AM
13	Confused	11/8/2021 7:57 AM
14	annoyed	11/8/2021 5:58 AM
15	There should be more effort for public trash management	11/8/2021 5:55 AM

Figure 12 Q4 Responses

Figure 13 Q5 Responses

Figure 14 Q6 Responses

Q7

Customize Save as

Do you think compressing method creates more space on those types of garbage ?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Yes	100.00%	16
No	0.00%	0
TOTAL		16

Figure 15 Q7 Responses

Q8

Customize Save as

Which solution would you rather for a trash bin ?

Answered: 16 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES	
Manually Compressing the trash	6.25%	1
Hydraulic Compressor that need someone to switch it on whenever it gets full	12.50%	2
Automatically Compress the trash using sensors	81.25%	13
TOTAL		16

Figure 16 Q8 Responses

Figure 17 Q9 Responses

Figure 18 Q10 Responses

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